

**A STUDY EMPLOYEE WELFARE MEASURE IN
DHANALAKSHIM SRINIVASAN HOTEL, PERAMBALUR**

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Abstract:

The project report titled "A Study on Employee Welfare Measures in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Hotel, Perambalur." The sample constitutes the permanent employee belonging to different departments. The data's were collected from primary sources. Primary data was collected through an administered questionnaire with twenty five questions. Census sampling technique was done to draw the sample size of 54 respondents from the 54 employees. The objectives considered for the study were to know the satisfaction level, awareness and utilization level of employee welfare provided by the organization. From the analysis, it is concluded that most of the employees are satisfied with the employee welfare measure provided by the organization. The organization is providing good welfare measure to the employees.

Key Words: Employee Welfare, Satisfaction, Facilities

Introduction:

Labour welfare, the term including far-reaching distinct administrations merits and offered facilities to employees by the employer. Labour welfare enhancing the health and work is for safety and all-purposive prosperity and efficiency of the specialists past the base norms lay down by work enactment. The concept of labor welfare is adaptable and versatile and varies broadly with times area to locale industry nation social qualities and traditions level and traditions level of industrialization and general social monetary advancement of people. The term labor welfare proposes numerous thoughts, which means and implications, for example, the state wealth wellbeing satisfaction respectability and the advancement of HR as an aggregate least level of welfare it is an appealing condition of existing including physical mental good and passionate prosperity. Labour welfare infers to giving better work conditions, for example, honest to good lighting, warm control, cleanliness, low commotion level, toilet and drinking water offices, flask and restroom prosperity and safety efforts. Welfare administrations, for example, lodging, training, amusement, transportation, and guiding.

"Welfare is a broad concept referring to a state of living of an individual or a group, in a desirable relationship with the total environment, ecological, economic, and social welfare includes both the social and economic contents.

The industrial progress depends on a satisfied labor force, and the importance of employee welfare measures. After the placement of the employees, they should be given proper training and programmers' to develop their efficiency so as to serve the organizations better. Welfare facilities are designed to take care of the well - being of the employees. They do not generally result only in monetary benefit. These welfare measures are provided by government Non - Government agencies and the employers.

Review of Literature:

David, A Decenzo (2001), "Personnel / Human Resource Management explained the various benefits and services provided by the companies to their employees. According to them, the legally required benefits and services include social security premiums, unemployment compensation, workers compensation and state disability programs. They felt that the cost of the voluntary benefits offered appears to be increasing.

Bindya Sukumar (2004), conducted a study "Labour Welfare Measures Adopted By Apollo Tyres Limited At Perambra". The company has total employee strength of 800. The workers work in three shifts i.e. Around 260 workers in each shift.

Punekar, Deodhar and Sankaran (2004), in their book, "Labor Welfare, Trade Unionism and Industrial Relations" stated that labor welfare is anything done for the comfort and improvement, intellectual and social well being of the employees over and above the wages paid which is not a necessity of the industry.

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Industrial Relations Journal (2005), Using British national survey data, this article assesses the impact of unions on management practices to reduce labour costs, implement high-performance work systems, and make employee welfare provisions. Relative to non-union workplaces, those with unions are found to have

practices which are consistent with 'mutual gains' outcomes.³ Staff development and employee welfare practices and their effect on productivity

Binoy Joseph, Josephinjodey (2009), studies in the article points out that, the structure of welfare states rests on a social security fabric. Government, employers, trade unions have done a lot to promote the betterment of workers conditions.

Scope of the Study:

- This study aims to find out the satisfaction of the employees, whether the company is providing necessary health, safety and welfare measures in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Hotel.
- This study helps to improve the performance of the Human resource management department.
- The scope of the study poses high scope by taking into consideration the exact deficiency of the welfare measures which can be identified and suitable recommendations can be made.
- This study can be used for understanding the potential of the workers. So that the survey is made all over the area of company and of this survey is made with both the male and female worker. This study also helps in manipulation of the basis expectation of the workers.
- This study will also help the researcher to gain some valuable knowledge over the company.

Needs and Importance:

- Welfare benefits are a necessity in every organization today. Employees have to be kept motivated at all times through various measure and activities. This strengthens their sense of belongingness and responsibility towards the company.
- To know the level of awareness of employee about the various welfare measures provided to them.
- To study how the welfare facilities provided help in increasing the services and job satisfaction.
- To offer useful suggestions for improving the effectiveness of welfare measures.

Objectives of the Study:

- To analyses the various welfare measures provided to the employee.
- To know their satisfactions towards the existing welfare measure.
- To analyses the excessive welfare measure provided to the employee.

Research Methodology:

Research is the process of systematic and in depth study or search of any particular topic, subject or area of investigation, backed by collection, compilation, Presentation and interpretation of relevant details or data. It is careful search or find out valuation facts, which would be useful for further application or utilization.

Research Design:

A research design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure. Regarding this project, descriptive research design concern with describing the perception of each individuals or narrating facts on welfare measures and diagnostic design helps in determine the frequency with which something occurs or it ISs associated with something else. These two research design help in understand the characteristic in a given situation. Think systematically about aspects in given situation, offers idea for probe and research help to make certain simple decision.

Sampling Design:

A sample design is a definite plan determined before any data are actually collected for obtaining a sample from a given population. Sampling is used to collect data from limited numbers whereas census is used for large numbers. For the research, sampling method was used. There are different types of sample design based on two factor namely the representation basis and the element selection technique .There are two main categories under which various sampling method can be put.

- Probability sampling.
- Non probability sampling In this particular research the A study is on probability sampling. And in the simple random sample is used.

Probability Sampling:

Probability sampling is based on the concept of random selection; the sample may be either unrestricted or restricted. When each sample elements is drawn individually from the population at large, then the sample so drawn is known as unrestricted samples, where as all other forms of sampling are covered under the term prestricted samples.

Non- Probability Sampling:

Non-probability sampling is that sampling procedure which does not afford any basis for estimating the probability that each item in the population has of being included in the sample.

Sample Size:

The total sample size of 54 has been taken for this study. Both male and female employees have been interviewed.

Data Collection Method:

Data are the basic input to any decision making processing of the gives statistics of importance of the study.

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data
- Secondary Data

Primary Data:

Primary data is known as the data collected for the first time through field survey. Such data are collected with specific set of objectives to assess the current status of any variable studied.

Secondary source of Data:

Secondary data means those data which were already collected and analyzed by someone else. Secondary data were collected records.

Statistical Tools and Techniques:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-Square Test

Research Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H0):

Null Hypothesis is formulated only to test whether there is any relationship between variables related to the problem being studied. Usually the null hypothesis usually is formed as a negative statement.

Alternate Hypothesis (H1):

Alternate Hypothesis (H1) is a statement, which is accepted after the null hypothesis is rejected based on the test result. The alternate hypothesis usually is formed as a positive statement.

Limitation of the Study:

- Available in statutory and non -statutory mode.
- Separate investments to be done for giving welfare benefits.
- Needs to be very well studied and analyzed.
- Should be flexible and not rigid.
- The respondents were unable or unwilling to give a complete and accurate response to certain questions.
- Some false information may be given by the respondents.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Work Place Airy and Comfortable:

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Highly Satisfied	10	18
2	Satisfied	42	78
3	Neutral	0	0
4	Dissatisfied	2	4
	Total	54	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

From the above analysis 18% of the labours tell that airy and comfortable work place is highly satisfied and 78% is telling that it's satisfied and 4% comes under dissatisfied level.

Chart:

Work Place Airy and Comfortable:

Chi Square:

- Null Hypothesis H0: There is no significant relationship between work experience and overall welfare satisfaction.
- Alternative Hypothesis H1: There is a significant relationship between work experience and overall welfare satisfaction.

Tables: Relationship between Work Experience of the Respondents and Overall Welfare Satisfaction work Experience

Overall Welfare Facilities Satisfaction	Less Than 1 Year	01-03 Years	04-06 Years	Above 7 Years	Grand Total
Yes	9	13	9	18	49
No	1	1	1	2	5
Column Total	10	14	10	20	54

Chi-Square Test Formula:

$$X^2 = \sum (O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$$

O_i = Observed Frequency

E_i = Expected Frequency

O _i	E _i	O _i -E _i	O _i -E _i ²	O _i -E _i ² /E _i
9	9.0740741	-0.0740741	5.486957	6.046851
13	12.703703	0.296296	0.087791	6.9107
9	9.0740741	-0.0740741	5.486957	6.046851
18	18.148148	-0.1481481	0.021947	1.209371
1	0.9259259	0.074074	5.486972	5.92593
1	1.2962963	-0.2962961	0.087791	0.067724
1	0.9259259	0.0740741	5.486972	5.92593
2	1.8518518	0.1481488	0.021947	0.011851
Total			22.16733	32.14521

Degree of Freedom = (r-1) (c-1)
 = (2-1) (4-1)
 = (1) (3)
 = (3)

Calculated Value = 32.15

For 3 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance, the chi-square table value is 7.81

Interpretation:

Calculated value > Table value

Hence H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted.

Findings:

- Majority of the respondents are aware about the statutory and non statutory Employee Welfare Facilities provided at the Company.
- Medical and First aid facilities provided by the Company are poor due to improper maintenance of medicines and first-aid facilities and very less number of physicians.
- Canteen facilities are good because the cleanliness maintained, proper storage of raw materials, food served is nutritious quality and quantity of food served is very good.
- Rating of the Uniform and Safety shoes provided by the company are satisfactory.
- Rest room facilities, maintenance and Recreational facilities are poor due to poor maintenance of cleanliness, less number of toilets, lack of provision of hot water facilities, sanitizers and tissues.
- The commitment of the company in Employee Welfare promotion is average.
- Respondents convey that the provision of Employee Welfare Facilities helps in motivation and productivity which brings belongingness to the Company, boosts employee morale and also provides job satisfaction.
- There is provision of sufficient drinking water to the workers and the water is easily accessible. The water provided is potable and water filters are situated inside the working premises and production areas.
- Ventilation, lighting, temperature, seating arrangement, and cleanliness inside the working area or the production area are satisfactory and good. There more number of windows and exhaust fans to keep the environment fresh, bright, cool and temperate.

Suggestions:

Recreation facilities should be provided to the workers to boost their morale and bring little diversion from their continuous routine work and to retard stress of the workers. Complete Medical facilities should be

given so as to minimize the absenteeism and to keep the employees more immunized and fit enough. Company should be more committed to promote welfare facilities as it creates more productivity which in turn benefits the company. Annual health checkup, employee counseling, various health camps, hospitalization facilities should be much more improved by conducting the health camps at least once in a month. The number of medical practitioners or physicians should be increased.

Conclusion:

Labor welfare covers an ample field and connotes a state of well-being, happiness, satisfaction, protection and enlargement of human resources and also helps to motivation of worker. The fundamental propose of labor welfare is to enrich the life of employees and to remain them joyful and conducted that helps to development of organization.

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